

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

ASSYRIAN FATHERS IN THE SERVICE OF THE GEORGIAN ORTHODOX CHURCH

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Abstract

In the middle of the 6th century, the Assyrian holy fathers arrived in Georgia and began to work, at the end of the 6th and beginning of the 7th centuries they actively operated in Georgia. If we compare the state in which the Georgian Church was at the time of the arrival of the Assyrian Fathers with that in which it was at the end of their activity, then we can be sure that they fought against the Monophysite trend and defeated it. Indeed, in the 30-40s of the 6th century, as scientists say, Monophysitism raged among us, in the 70s-90s of the same century and at the beginning of the 7th century Georgia was completely Chalcedonian, which is the result of the merit of the Assyrian fathers, along with political reasons.

In what years the Assyrian fathers came to Georgia, what was the religious direction of the Georgian Church at that time, and what was the situation at the end of their activity - this is the subject of our discussion.

Keywords: Church, Assyrian fathers, Christianity, Georgia

The Assyrian fathers came to Georgia during the reign of King Farsman and Catholicos Yevlav. The Life of the Saints writes that the Reverend Father Ioane of Zedazeni and his twelve disciples "were gladly received by the Georgian people by King Farsman (542-557) and Catholic Archbishop Yevlav of Kartli (533-544). The chronicle informs us that the Holy Fathers of Cappadocia addressed the audience in the Georgian language "... Ioane of Zedazeni was executed approximately between 557-60 years, during the time of Makarios Catholicos of Kartli (553-559)". Russian church historiography, relying on Georgian chronicles, believes that the Assyrian fathers arrived in Georgia in the 540s. This is the time when Persian rule in Kartli reaches its full strength. "In 542, Khosro came to Kartli with a huge army and suddenly moved from there to Egris, thus violating the "eternal truce".

This is the era when the Persians were forced to abandon the spread of Mazdeanism in Transcaucasia and instead became the patrons of Monophysite Christianity, church writings were attributed to them, preaching Monophysite ideas and the need for an inextricable connection with Persia. To this end, the agents of the king of Persia made up legends that Christianity was introduced into Armenia, Kartli and Albania by one person allegedly connected with Persia. The Monophysites mercilessly slandered the writings of the dyophysites, that is, the Chalcedonists... The Persian government also used other means to strengthen this ideological connection. They wanted, for example, to unite the churches of Armenia, Kartli and Albania, so that it would be easier for Persian officials to manage them. Ivane Javakhishvili considers the date of arrival of the Assyrian fathers in Georgia to be the 540s. "... the Assyrian fathers were not supposed to come all together and at the same time, but for the first time David of

Garedji travelled, then Ioane of Zedazeni with his disciples - in the middle of the 6th century. It seems that Anton of Martkofi appeared on his own around the same time, ..."

"The date of the arrival of Ioane of Zedazeni and his disciples is 540 BC". Received this date is based on the years 521-596 of the reign of Svimon the Mesvete and on the reign of Farsman. M. Brose agrees with Ivane Javakhishvili. According to T. Jordania, "the apprenticeship and settlement of Ioane of Zedazeni in Georgia took place in 541-557, when the Monophysite Armenians raged in Georgia. The Church was in a dangerous position for the Georgians, and this circumstance, in my opinion, prompted the Assyrian fathers to bring themselves sacrifice and go to defend our country from heretics...". According to the "Life of Kartli": "... four hundred and twenty years later, the holy father Arseniy Catholicos of Kartli was interrogated and investigated ..." According to K. Kekelidze, he professed Catholicism in 955-980. If you subtract 420 years from his date of birth, then you really get 540 years. K. Kekelidze writes that "according to today's estimates, he came to us in the forties..."

"Life of Kartli" writes "Catholicos died an old man, and the same Farsman king appointed Saba", "from the Mesopotamia came Ioane called Zedazeni, the Enlightener of Kartli, the builder of churches, who worked many miracles, he and his disciples... , Anton from Martkopi, Ise from Tsilkani, Tate from Stefantsmida, Shio from Mgvime, Isidore from Samtave, Abibos from Nekresi, Michael from Ulumbo, Piros from Breti and Elia Deacon".

According to the 'Life of Kartli', the arrival of the Assyrian fathers in Georgia almost coincides with the new rule introduced in the Georgian Church, Catholics were no longer brought from Greece, but Georgians were elected on the spot. Permission to introduce this

new rule was allegedly given to Emperor Justinian (527-565), but Justinian had no right to Kartli because the Persians ruled there. It seems that the Persian authorities forbade the visit of the Greek bishop to Kartli, but did not interfere with the election of the Georgian Catholicos. This practice was accepted and not recognized by the Byzantine royal court, because the autocephalous Georgian Church was much more acceptable to him than the abolition or the very restriction of the autocephaly of the Georgian Church and the subordination of its pro-Persian orientation (Eastern Armenian) Church. The ban on the arrival of the Catholicos from Greece still meant the separation of the Georgian Church from the Greco-Roman. The purpose of the united meetings of the Transcaucasian churches, which were repeatedly held in 506-532, was the religious and hierarchical subordination of the Georgian church to the pro-Persian Catholicos Dvini. The strengthening of Monophysitism was followed by persecution of dyophysitism in Kartli. Shortly thereafter, in the 540s, the Assyrian Fathers arrived. From the point of view of Ivane Javakhishvili, according to the writings of ancient Georgian authors, the goal of the Assyrian fathers "...was to strengthen Eastern Georgia with "faith and truth", i.e. They came to strengthen Orthodoxy.

"In IX-XII centuries for Georgian writers, the only "true faith" was Chalcedonianism, and when they say that the Assyrian fathers prayed for the strengthening of the "true faith", it means that they fought for the victory of Chalcedonism, so their "cleansing the soule" must mean also the fight against Monophysitism. Ivane Javakhishvili concludes: "... the Assyrian fathers, who came under the leadership of Ioane of Zedazeni, were not only Monophysites, but also constant enemies of the Monophysites. " Almost all researchers admit that Monophysitism won in Kartli in the first half of the VI century. Does this mean that Chalcedonism in Georgia at that time completely disappeared? No, not only part of the population was Chalcedonian, but the bishops themselves and a significant number of bishoprics were Chalcedonian. "... The Chalcedonians were not defeated by the victory of Monophysitism in Georgia, as we were sure, 9 bishops were not present at this meeting ", they did not sign the protocols. Undoubtedly, their actions and struggle would not have stopped even after that. In an anonymous letter from ending of the 7th century ... it is mentioned that the Monophysites who returned to Armenia from Byzantium in 574 asked the Georgians and Albanians to accept Chalcedonism with them, but both Albanians and Georgians refused. This circumstance is already a harbinger of change in Georgia."

"...by 574, the forces of Monophysitism in Georgia seem to have already been shaken, and Chalcedonism has already won sympathy in Georgian church circles. The fact of the work of the Assyrian Fathers makes it easier for us to understand this victory of Chalcedonism in Georgia. Just as the Assyrian monks left their homeland to preach their Chalcedonian faith and came to preach in Albania, the same thing happened in Georgia and the Assyrian fathers came. The internal religious struggle, the energetic work of the Assyrian fathers and the strong influence of a political

orientation that clearly veered towards Byzantium, allowed Chalcedonism to triumph over Monophysitism in Georgia. Not if in 574, but even earlier, immediately after the arrival of the Assyrian fathers in Georgia, in particular, at the beginning of the second half of the 6th century, disagreements arose between the Georgian and Armenian churches, the Armenian Church became the leading church in Transcaucasia at the request of Iran, which had influence on the Georgian and Albanian churches from a certain point of view, therefore, disagreement with the Armenian Church also meant opposition to Iran. "... the first signs of discord appeared at the beginning of the second half of the 6th century, when the Armenian Church recognized the supremacy of Iran, and the left trend of Monophysitism in the local community of Dvini declared Evtlianism as their official religion. The churches of Kartli and Albania did not support the definitions of the Dvina Council, did not condemn the Council of Chalcedon At the end of the 60s of the 6th century, the Iranian Empire again tried to unite a single Monophysite camp against Byzantium in Transcaucasia ... " was founded in 551 in Dvin, during the time of Catholicos Nerse Mijin. In 551 the Georgian Church did not agree with the Council of Chalcedon demanded of it, but did not take a firm anti-Monophysite position, instead, according to Arseny of Safari, the Georgian Church completely severed its hierarchical connection with the Armenian Church in 551, because, in turn, the Armenian Church severed its hierarchical connection with the Greek Church. If we look at the situation that has developed in the Georgian Church, we will see that by the time the Assyrian Fathers came to Georgia in the 540s, Monophysitism had certain positions in us, ten years later, thanks to the activities of the Assyrian Father, the positions of Chalcedonism in us are stronger than monophysitism, which appeared at the council in 551. 20 year later, in 574, Chalcedonism was victorious in the Georgian Church. Thanks to the efforts of the Assyrian Fathers for 30 years, they managed not only to achieve the complete victory of Chalcedonism, but, no less important, the victory of Chalcedonism created a theoretical basis for the mutual separation of the Georgians and the Armenian Churches, and the Armenian Church tried to spread its language and culture throughout the Iranian Transcaucasus, thanks to which the Assyrian fathers with their labour strengthened the national basis of Georgian culture and avoided the obvious threat of national-cultural degeneration.

"On the nationality of the Assyrian fathers, D. Bakradze said: "Now in our literature there is an opinion that ten or thirteen fathers were Georgians by kinship. In our opinion, this opinion is not unfounded. As proof of this, on the one hand, he cites the opinion that "in ancient times, Georgian hermits and translators worked in Antioch and its environs for the benefit of their estate" - on the other hand, that the Assyrian fathers "whether they come to Georgia or not, they say in Georgian, serve and preach in Georgian The Georgian people themselves..." Perhaps the Assyrian fathers were not Georgians, they was speaking Georgian, worship, bringing the Georgian language to the fore and paying special attention to it should have been caused

not by national, but by religious opinion. The fact is that already at that time, i.e. in the middle of the VI century, the Greek language was banned in the Persian Empire, it could not be used during the liturgy and sacred services, like the language of Chalcedon. Back in the 5th century, the Greek language was strictly forbidden - as Moses of Khoreni writes. It is known that in the 6th century in the Persian Empire the languages allowed for worship by Christians were Armenian and Assyrian. A century earlier, Persia had demanded that the Armenians adopt Assyrian worship instead of Greek. Books in Greek were burned, speaking Greek was forbidden. This was before the introduction of the Armenian alphabet - before 405. After the introduction of the Armenian alphabet, Persia banned translations from Greek and the use of Greek books. At that time, services in Armenian and Assyrian were allowed, while those in Greek were prohibited. In the 6th century, during the conquest of Georgia by the Persians, Greek-language services and translations from Greek were banned, as in other parts of the empire. At first, Georgian-language worship was not prohibited, but after the majority of Georgians became confessors of the Chalcedonian religion, persecution of the Georgian language began, since Georgian and Greek would be considered Chalcedonian languages, and Armenian and Assyrian languages as Monophysite languages. Mutual friendship and love of Georgians and Greeks were not unknown to the Persians of those centuries. From the martyrdom of St. Razhden, it is clear that the Georgians were persecuted as friends of the Greeks. The Georgian language was persecuted as a carrier language of Chalcedonism, just like Greek. That is why the Assyrian Fathers pay special attention to the Georgian language. For them, the Georgian language is an instrument of Chalcedonism. This weapon is especially useful. Dyophysitism was quite strong and influential in Armenia, but Monophysitism was stronger and therefore became a national faith. In Georgia, from the middle of the 6th century, the situation was the opposite. In our country, although Monophysitism was strong and supported by Persia itself, dyophysitism gained strength and became a national belief. For this reason, the population living in Georgia, who were Monophysite in faith, but Georgian in nationality, considered themselves non-Georgian, i.e. Church of Chalcedon, and Armenian, i.e. monophysite church. Georgian by nationality, but monophysite by religion, after the influence of Persia on Kartli decreased, in order to protect their faith, the population studied the Armenian language, shared the Armenian church culture, defended the positions of the Armenian language in their church, recognized Armenian as the language of worship. This was the reason for the speech of the Armenian-speaking Georgian population of Tsurtavi against the language reform of Kirion. The inhabitants of Tsurtavi, did not receive with great joy one of the Syrian fathers, David of Garedji. The local leader Bubakar even promised to kill him. About the church Armenian language of the local population in the life of David of Garedji left a trace. David's goal was to chalcedony the local Georgians, which was generally not achieved. This is indi-

cated by the introduction of the Georgian church language by Kirion in these areas at the beginning of the 7th century. Year 614 After the Persian Council, the Christians of the Persian Empire were ordered to submit to the Armenian Church, that is, to accept Monophysitism. Georgia and its royal court, obviously, would have been forced to obey this command of the empire, to recognize the Armenian faith - monophysitism. For this reason, the king of Kartli, i.e. the leader Stefanoz, must have been a Monophysite, which we seem to have a hint of in the life of Shio the Mgvime Stephanoz "left the Greeks and joined the Persians". He "was unfaithful and did not fear God", "did not want to retreat from the Persians", Hercules, the Greek Caesar, deprived him of royal power. Therefore, it is not surprising that such an unfaithful king is not afraid of the monks of Mghvime and does not come into conflict with him. It can be seen that even with the greatest strengthening of the Persians, when at the beginning of the 7th century Persia successfully attacked Byzantium, conquered its lands and even took Jerusalem, the monasteries founded by the Assyrian fathers still remain centers of Chalcedonism, and even the non-Chalcedonian commander-in-chief feels his power. K. Kekelidze believes that the Assyrian Fathers carried out their activities through monasteries - "there is no evidence that before the arrival of the so-called thirteen fathers there were monasteries in the true sense of the word. Monasteries were founded among us for the first time by the named fathers ... "According to the testimony of the old writer Vasily Vachesdze, writes K. Kekelidze, "thirteen Assyrian fathers showed so many feats and miracles that if they had a place among the Greeks, they would hardly have written books for the account", i.e. they wrote about it, but no one in our country took care of this because "the relatives of the Georgians are simple". Strengthening the faith was the main merit of the Assyrian fathers. The nun Macrine, who generally expresses the point of view of the Church, writes that the Assyrian fathers "confirmed and renewed the faith preached by Nino."

The restoration of the faith preached by Nino was the main merit of the Syrian fathers. Therefore, on the opinion of Iv. Javakhishvili, according to which the Assyrian fathers had to be dyophysites, and it was to strengthen the position of the Chalcedonites (dyophysites) that they had to go to Georgia, which became the scene of sharp religious contradictions. In this case, the sharp turn of the Georgian Church towards dyophysitism at the end of the 7th century can be presented as a completely natural result of their activities.

True, the dominance of Monophysitism left its mark on the Georgian Church for several decades during the 6th century and at the beginning of the 7th century, but thanks to the strength and stability of the Georgian people as a whole, heresy did not succeed in Georgia, which Georgian scholars proudly noted. "It should be said that in the development of the religious history of the Georgian people from the 8th century onwards, and even more so in the 10th-11th centuries, strict comrade Orthodoxy prevailed. In this age, doctrines were established and legitimized, which were considered

certain inevitable truths about the past of this issue. According to this provision, if in another place Christianity was repeatedly struck by heresies, and this or that heresy more than once prevailed, not from one place, but in Georgia, the people of Georgia preserved the preaching and teaching received from the first as unchanging and serene. Ancient Georgian scholars did not hide or colour the state of the church in the specified period, for example, George the Less, who in his work quotes the words of George of Mtatsminda, referring to the power of the Monophysite heresy, that is, the Armenian Church, over the Georgian Church in certain periods of the 6th and 7th centuries. According to him, "from the very beginning we had the Holy Scriptures and faith, which were true and correct," which were later violated by the intensification of the Monophysite heresy in Kartli, and sacred books correctly translated from the Greek language in the 4th-5th centuries were translated or corrected from Armenian in the 6th-7th centuries.

The merit of the Assyrian Fathers was that they averted a great danger for the Georgian Church from the recognition of Monophysitism, or, as it was called at that time, the recognition of the Armenian faith.

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